

INTRODUCTION SELECTION OF BEAN PLANT, EVALUATION OF GRAIN QUALITY AND STUDY OF STORAGE PROCESSES

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Annotation.

During the growth period, black bean goes through several stages of development, which differ in terms of quality, and this factor also affects the nutrition process. Black moss has development periods consisting of germination, flowering, fruiting and ripening. The results of the study of how external environmental factors affect the yield of black mallow and the development of black mallow during the growing season indicate that the life of the plant can be divided into six periods. Plants do not always require the same amount of nutrients, either in terms of quantity or quality. This factor varies depending on the growth and development of the plant and the time of the season in general. In this regard, all field crops are divided into two groups, short and long feeding during the growing season. In particular, the black moss plant is considered a plant that is fed for a long time during the growing season. It absorbs nutrients from the soil from the time it germinates from the seed until the end of the growing season. After the autumn frost hits the black mallow plant planted as a repeated crop, its growth period ends, and the black mallow seed planted in the ground in the middle of the spring season usually goes through a full vegetation period.

Key words.

bean, growth period, nutrition, seed germination, weeding, flowering, germination and ripening periods, nutrient uptake, fertilizer efficiency, bean stalks.

Beans are rich in nutrients and is also a good source of fiber. These plants are commonly found in home gardens as they are not fussy and are easy to grow. These plants are among some of the fastest growing plants in the world. These plants grow and mature at a faster pace, as compared to many other vegetable plants.

How to Plant Common Beans

When to Plant

The most important rule of growing common beans is not to plant too early. Plant in the spring after all danger of frost has passed. Seeds sown too early can rot in cold, damp soil, and the plants need warm weather to thrive.

Selecting a Planting Site

Choose a planting site that gets lots of sun and has organically rich soil with sharp drainage. Make sure there are no tall shrubs or trees nearby that will create too much shade for the beans. Beans also can be grown in raised beds and containers.

Spacing, Depth, and Support

In general, plant seeds about an inch deep, and position nursery plants at the same depth they were in their previous container.

- Bush beans can be planted in rows 2.5 to 3 feet apart, with seeds placed 1 to 2 inches apart. After the plants germinate, thin the seedlings to 3 to 4 inches apart.
- Pole beans need some type of support on which to grow. The support should be 6 to 8 feet tall. Be sure the support is in place before you seed. Space supports roughly 3 to 4 feet apart.

Common Bean Care

Light

Beans need full sun for the best yield. Full sun also helps to keep the plants dry and less likely to be affected by certain issues, such as fungal diseases.

Soil

Beans like organically rich loamy soil with a slightly acidic pH. Good soil drainage also is key. Remove weeds prior to planting to prevent competition for soil nutrients and moisture. As the beans grow, weed carefully around the plants, as their shallow roots can be easily damaged.

Water

Common beans need 1 inch of water per week. Use a drip irrigation system for supplemental watering to avoid splashing soil onto the leaves, which can lead to soil-borne diseases. To determine whether the plants need water, stick your finger about 1 inch into the soil near the base of the plant. If the soil is dry, it's time to water. Plants that are underwatered will stop flowering. Beans have shallow roots, and mulching can help to keep them cool and preserve moisture in the soil.

Temperature and Humidity

Common beans germinate best when the soil temperature is between 70 and 80 degrees. If the soil temperature is below 60 degrees, seeds will germinate more slowly and are susceptible to rot. The plants grow best when the air temperature is

between 65 and 85 degrees. Beans tend to stop flowering in the extreme heat of summer. But keep them well-watered, and they will resume flowering and production when temperatures cool. Moreover, common beans grow in all humidity conditions if properly watered.

Fertilizer

As legumes, beans fix nitrogen in the soil, so avoid a high-nitrogen fertilizer. Instead, use a 10-20-10 fertilizer to feed the plants throughout the growing season, following the product directions. Pole beans produce over such a long period that they also will benefit from a side dressing of compost about halfway through their growing season.

Pollination

Most bean varieties are self-pollinators. The blossoms are so-called "perfect flowers" that include both male and female parts. Pollination within each flower usually happens reliably just from gentle breezes, though bees and other pollinators can assist in the process. But it is not necessary to grow different varieties or multiple plants in order to ensure cross-pollination, as is the case with some species.

Types of Common Beans

In the most popular pod/snap category, there are several types of common beans, including:

- 'Kentucky Wonder': This old pole variety of string bean is prized for its flavor.
- 'Bountiful': This is an early-producing, stringless heirloom bush bean.
- 'Golden Wax Bean': This is a soft-textured, yellow bush bean.
- 'Royal Burgundy': An early-producing bush bean, it has purple pods that turn green when cooked.
- 'Romano': This classic broad, Italian-style, bush or pole bean has a meaty flavor.

Pod/Snap Beans vs. Shell Beans vs. Dry Beans

The various varieties of *Phaseolus vulgaris* are categorized into three types:

- Pod/snap beans: These are the most popular beans for most gardeners, comprising both low-growing bush beans and tall pole beans in which the entire pods are prepared and consumed whole—outer pod as well as inner seeds. This group represents what most people think of as green beans. Bush varieties typically grow 18 to 30 inches tall and are self-supporting, while pole varieties have vines that can climb or sprawl as much as 15 feet.

- Shell beans: With this type, the pod is not eaten, but rather the beans are removed from the pod as they approach maturity. The beans are prepared and eaten while still soft.
- Dry beans: Including kidney beans, white beans, yellow beans, navy beans, and pinto beans, the varieties in this group are generally shelled and stored dry or canned for later use. 3

It's important to distinguish between these types, as it will dictate how you prepare and eat them. Make sure to buy a variety that fits your expectations.

Harvesting Common Beans

Harvesting beans is an ongoing task, and the more you pick, the more beans the plants will set. You can start to harvest anytime after the beans form. Gardeners usually harvest the beans when the pods are young and tender, about the size of a small pencil. The inner seeds should not yet be visible through the pods. Overly mature beans, where the inner seeds can be seen bulging through the walls of the pod, can be tough and stringy.

In general, bush beans are ready to pick in 50 to 55 days after planting. Pole beans will take 55 to 65 days, depending on the variety. Check the packet to be sure your choice will have time to mature in your growing season. Harvest by gently pulling each bean from the vine or by snapping them off at the vine end. Be careful not to damage the plant when harvesting. You can cook the beans right away or blanch and freeze them. They can keep in the freezer for up to a year.

How to Grow Common Beans in Pots

Growing beans in a container can be helpful, especially when it comes time to regularly harvest your crop. As long as the container gets enough sunlight, you can place it in a spot that's convenient for you to visit regularly.

Choose one of the smaller bean varieties if you wish to grow them in containers, and be sure to give pole beans a support structure on which to grow. Aim for a container that is at least 1 foot deep with ample drainage holes. An unglazed clay container is ideal because it will allow excess soil moisture to evaporate through its walls. Wood barrels also can make good planters.

Pruning

No pruning is necessary for common beans, other than pulling the plants from the ground as cold weather sets in. These are annual plants that do not return the following spring. Allow the beans to continue to grow as long as possible, as these legumes actually improve the soil by absorbing nitrogen from the air and fixing it in the soil. Some gardeners like to rotate the planting location of legume species like

beans and peas around the garden to take advantage of this soil-improving property.

Propagating Common Beans

Bean plants are propagated via seed. Because the plants are annuals, this is an inexpensive way to ensure you have new plants each year. Here's how to save the seeds:

1. Harvest seed pods from a healthy bean plant once the pods have dried and become brittle.
2. Break open the pods to release the seeds.
3. Store the seeds in a dark, dry, cool spot within an airtight container. They should be viable for three to four years and can be planted in the spring after the threat of frost has passed.

Be aware, however, that only non-hybrid, open-pollinated plants will produce seeds that grow into plants identical to the parents. If you try this with hybrid varieties, you are likely to be disappointed with plants that do not have the same characteristics as the parent plant.

Common Pests and Plant Diseases

Several animal pests love bean plants, including:

- Mexican bean beetles will eat the flowers, the beans, and especially the leaves.
- Spider mites pierce the leaf surface and suck the sap, often causing leaves to die.
- Japanese beetles and aphids may also attack bean plants.
- Bean leaf beetles can girdle the stems near the soil line and chew holes in the plant's leaves.
- Deer and groundhogs will eat entire bean plants, and fencing is necessary to stop them if they are prevalent in your area.

Fungal diseases, such as *Alternaria* leaf spot, can be a problem in damp conditions. Other diseases, including white mold, bean rust, and mosaic virus, can also affect bean plants. Help prevent diseases by keeping the vines dry. Also, don't overcrowd the plants, and provide plenty of air circulation. You can look for plant varieties that are bred for disease resistance.

REFERENCES:

1. Ubaidullaev M.M.U., Askarov Kh.Kh., Mirzaikromov M.A.U. EFFECTIVENESS OF NEW DEFOLIANTS. Theoretical & Applied Science. 2021. No. 12 (104). S. 789-792. https://www.elibrary.ru/keyword_items.asp?id=21526423
2. Nazirova Rakhnamokhan Mukhtarovna, Mirzaikromov Mirzababur Alisher Ugli, Usmanov Nodirjon Botiraliyevich Vliyanie processa okhlajdeniya zerna kukuruzy na ego sokhranyaemost, kolichestvo poter i na zarajyonnost nasekomymi-vreditelyami // Problemy Nauki. 2020. No. 6-2 (151). URL: <https://cyberleninka.ru/article/n/vliyanie-protsesa-ohlazhdeniya-zerna-kukuruzy-na-ego-sohranyaemost-kolichestvo-poter-i-na-zarajyonnost-nasekomymi-vreditelyami>
3. Mirzayeva, M. A., Mullajonova, S. S., & Mirzaikromov, M. A. (2022). THE GRAPE PROCESSING TECHNOLOGY FOR WINE PRODUCTION. International Journal of Advance Scientific Research, 2(04), 7-10. <https://sciencebring.com/index.php/ijasr/article/view/43/33>
4. Mirzaikromov M.A. VLIYANIE ORGANICHESKIX I MINERALNYX UDOBRENIY NA UROJAYNOST HLOPKA // Universum: tekhnicheskie nauki: elektron. nauchn. journal. 2022. 5(98). URL: <https://7universum.com/ru/tech/archive/item/13724>
5. Mirzaikromov, M. A. (2023). EFFECT OF DETONATION SOIL SOFTENING ON CARBONATE AND SULFATE SALTS. Open Access Repository, 4(04), 41-52. https://scholar.google.ru/citations?view_op=view_citation&hl=ru&user=tmV-6nwAAAAJ&citation_for_view=tmV-6nwAAAAJ:FxGoFyZp5QC